

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 82:0 A Psalm of Asaph.</p>	
<p>Psa. 82:1 God takes His ^astand in ¹His own congregation; He ^bjudges in the midst of the ^{2c}rulers.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 82:1</p> <p>מִזְמוֹר לְאַסָּף אֱלֹהִים נֹצֵב בְּעֵדֶת־אֱלֹהִים בְּקִרְבֹּת אֱלֹהִים יִשְׁפֹּט : ² עַד־מִתִּי הַשֹּׁפֵט עוֹל וּפְנֵי רָשָׁעִים תִּשְׁאוּ־סֵלָה : ³ שֹׁפֵט־דָּל וַיִּתּוֹם עָנִי וְרֵשׁ הַצְּדִיקִים : ⁴ פִּלְטוּ־דָּל וְאַבְיוֹן מִיַּד רָשָׁעִים הַצֵּילוּ : ⁵ לֹא יִדְעוּ אִלֵּא יִבְיִנוּ בַחֲשֹׁכָה יִתְהַלְכוּ יִמּוּטוּ כָּל־מוֹסְרֵי אָרֶץ : ⁶ אֲנִי־ אֲמַרְתִּי אֱלֹהִים אַתֶּם וּבְנֵי עֲלִיּוֹן כְּלַכְּם : ⁷ אֲכֵן כְּאַדָּם הִמּוֹתוֹן וּכְאַחַד הַשָּׂרִים תִּפְלוּ : ⁸ קוּמָה אֱלֹהִים שֹׁפֵט הָאָרֶץ כִּי־אַתָּה תִּנְחַל בְּכָל־הַגּוֹיִם :</p>
<p>² How long will you ^ajudge unjustly And ^bshow partiality to the wicked? ¹Selah.</p>	
<p>³ ^aVindicate the weak and fatherless; Do justice to the afflicted and destitute.</p>	
<p>⁴ ^aRescue the weak and needy; Deliver <i>them</i> out of the hand of the wicked.</p>	
<p>Psa. 82:5 They ^ado not know nor do they understand; They ^bwalk about in darkness; All the ^cfoundations of the earth are shaken.</p>	
<p>⁶ ¹I ^asaid, “You are gods, And all of you are ^bsons of the Most High.</p>	
<p>⁷ “Nevertheless ^ayou will die like men And fall like <i>any</i> ^bone of the princes.”</p>	
<p>⁸ ^aArise, O God, ^bjudge the earth! For it is You who ^cpossesses all the nations.</p>	

References

Psalm 82:1

¹Lit *the congregation of God*

²Lit *gods*

^aIs 3:13

^b2 Chr 19:6; Ps 58:11

^cEx 21:6; 22:8, 28

Psalm 82:2

¹*Selah* may mean: *Pause, Crescendo* or *Musical interlude*

^aPs 58:1

^bDeut 1:17; Prov 18:5

Psalm 82:3

^aDeut 24:17; Ps 10:18; Is 11:4; Jer 22:16

Psalm 82:4

^aJob 29:12

Psalm 82:5

^aPs 14:4; Jer 4:22; Mic 3:1

^bProv 2:13; Is 59:9; Jer 23:12

^cPs 11:3

Psalm 82:6

¹Lit *I, on my part*

^aPs 82:1; John 10:34

^bPs 89:26

Psalm 82:7

^aJob 21:32; Ps 49:12; Ezek 31:14

^bPs 83:11

Psalm 82:8

^aPs 12:5

^bPs 58:11; 96:13

^cPs 2:8; Rev 11:15

Targum

Psa. 82:1 A hymn composed by Asaph. God, his presence abides in the assembly of the righteous who are strong in Torah; he will give judgment in the midst of the righteous judges. ² How long, O wicked, will you judge falsely, and lift up the faces of the wicked forever? ³ Judge the poor and the orphan; acquit the needy and the poor. ⁴ Save the poor and needy, from the hands of the wicked deliver them. ⁵ They do not know how to do good, and they do not understand the Torah, they walk in darkness; because of this, the pillars of the earth's foundations shake. ⁶ I said, "You are reckoned as angels, and all of you are like angels of the height." ⁷ But truly you will die like the sons of men; and like one of the leaders you will fall. ⁸ Arise, O LORD, judge all the inhabitants of the earth; for you will possess all the Gentiles.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm is a vigorous affirmation of the Torah judicial system and a forceful condemnation of persons who try to corrupt the LORD's Laws. The Talmud, Rosh Hashanah 31a), designates this as the "Song of the Day" for the third day of the week. This is because, on the third day of Creation, the LORD uncovered the earth with His wisdom. This alludes to Genesis 1:9, where the LORD allowed the water to reveal land.

The sage Maharsha explained that the earth's continued existence depends on maintaining equity and justice. In the Pirkei Avos (Ethics of the Fathers 1:10), we learn that the world endures because of truth, justice, and peace. In the Talmud Shabbos 10a, every judge who renders true justice becomes a partner of the LORD in the work of Creation.

Superscript and verse one

There is nothing that reveals the LORD more clearly as the founder and maintainer of human society than justice which was ingrained into the spirit and conscience of man at the time of Creation.

A Psalm of Asaf. God stands in every tribunal of God; He judges in the midst of the judges.

Verse two

How long will you enforce violence in your judgment and respect the persons of the lawless? Meditate on this verse.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

